

Financial Literacy And Investment Decisions Among Women Employees In Healthcare Product Manufacturing Factories In Thiruvananthapuram

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Abstract

Making effective investment decisions requires adequate financial knowledge and awareness. This study examines the relationship between financial literacy and investment decisions among women employees working in healthcare product manufacturing companies in Thiruvananthapuram. The research was conducted among women workers from ten selected companies, with a final sample of 412 respondents. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using simple percentage analysis, mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, t-test, One-way ANOVA, and regression analysis to determine the influence of various dimensions of financial literacy on investment behaviour. The findings reveal that most respondents possess a moderate level of financial literacy, demonstrating good awareness of investment avenues and basic financial concepts but limited understanding of analytical skills, risk-return relationships, and economic policies. The results show that age and educational qualification significantly influence financial literacy, while investment experience and annual investment positively affect investment decisions. Regression analysis confirms that risk-return awareness, financial behaviour, product knowledge, and digital literacy have a substantial impact on investment decision-making. The study concludes that financial literacy plays a vital role in shaping women's investment attitudes and decisions. Women with higher financial literacy tend to make more confident, informed, and independent investment choices. The study suggests that enhancing financial education and digital financial training can empower female industrial workers, promote financial inclusion, and contribute to their long-term economic security and financial well-being.

Key words: Financial Literacy, Investment Decisions, Financial Behaviour, Risk-Return Awareness, Digital Financial Literacy, Investment Attitude.

INTRODUCTION

Financial literacy has emerged as a crucial life skill in the modern economic environment, influencing how individuals manage income, savings, credit, and investments. In an era marked by increasing financial products and services, understanding financial concepts and making informed decisions have become vital for personal and professional well-being. Financial literacy not only empowers individuals to make rational investment decisions but also enhances their ability to plan for the future, manage risks, and achieve financial security. Women, particularly those employed in the manufacturing sector, often face unique financial challenges due to income disparities, limited access to financial education, and socio-economic constraints. Female workers in healthcare product manufacturing factories, who contribute significantly to both household and industrial productivity, frequently operate within modest income brackets and limited financial awareness. Their

investment behavior is often influenced by traditional saving habits, risk aversion, and lack of exposure to financial instruments.

In Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, a region known for its high literacy rate and expanding industrial base, female participation in manufacturing sectors has grown steadily. However, the extent of financial literacy among these workers and its impact on their investment decisions remains underexplored. Understanding this relationship is vital for promoting inclusive financial development and empowering women economically. This study, therefore, seeks to analyze the level of financial literacy among female workers employed in healthcare product manufacturing factories in Thiruvananthapuram and to examine how their financial knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors influence their investment decisions. The findings will help identify the gaps in financial awareness and provide insights for designing targeted financial education programs to enhance women's financial empowerment and economic stability.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Adil M., Singh Y., and Ansari M.S. (2022) investigated how financial literacy moderates the relationship between behavioural biases and investment decisions among male and female investors in the Delhi-NCR region. The study found that financial literacy significantly influenced investment decisions for both genders, with men displaying higher overconfidence and women exhibiting stronger risk aversion and herding tendencies. Moreover, financial literacy was found to mitigate irrational investment behaviour and enhance rational decision-making. The findings emphasized the necessity of financial education programs, workshops, and seminars to reduce the impact of behavioural biases.

Dasani L., and Bokephode S. (2023) examined the relationship between financial literacy and investment decisions in the Indian context. The study evidenced that individuals with higher financial literacy levels prefer diverse and risk-oriented investment options such as mutual funds and insurance-linked schemes, whereas those with lower literacy tend to invest in traditional instruments like bank deposits and post office schemes. The study concluded that financial education should begin at the school level to nurture a financially literate population capable of making informed investment decisions. **Harinakshi and Goveas C. (2023)** conducted a comprehensive systematic literature review on financial literacy, investment behaviour, and risk tolerance among Indian women investors. The review highlighted that education, income, and financial awareness significantly influenced women's investment behaviour. Despite increasing participation, women continue to face barriers like limited financial knowledge, dependence on family advice, and lack of confidence in independent decision-making.

Iram, Bilal, and Ahmad (2023) explored the mediating role of financial literacy between women entrepreneurs' behavioural biases and their investment decision-making in Pakistan. Findings of the study revealed that financial literacy significantly mediated the relationship between overconfidence and availability heuristics with investment decisions, enhancing rational decision-making. Conversely, representativeness and anchoring biases showed no significant mediation through financial literacy. **Sundarasan S., et al (2023)** conducted a bibliometric and content analysis to explore the evolving research landscape on women's financial literacy. The study revealed that although global awareness of financial literacy has increased, women still face significant barriers related to cultural, socioeconomic, and educational factors. Financial literacy was found to be a key driver for women's empowerment, economic security, and independence. **Anggraini A., Anggraini N., and Suroto (2024)** analyzed the mediating role of financial self-efficacy between financial inclusion, financial literacy, and investment behaviour among banking

employees in Jakarta. The study found that financial inclusion significantly influenced financial self-efficacy, while financial literacy does not. Moreover, financial literacy showed a strong and direct impact on investment decisions, whereas financial inclusion and financial self-efficacy had no significant direct or mediating effects on investment behaviour. **Gusti G.P., Giriati, and Wendy (2024)** investigated the influence of financial literacy on investment decisions among investors in Indonesia. The findings of the study revealed that financial literacy has a positive and significant impact on investment decisions, indicating that individuals with higher financial understanding make more informed and rational investment choices. The study also noted that younger investors tend to make better investment decisions, while education and income levels showed no significant influence.

Sharma M., Damseth A., and Shyam I. (2024) examined the relationship between financial literacy and investment decisions among youth in Himachal Pradesh using age as a moderating factor. The study found that age plays a crucial role in shaping financial awareness, information-seeking behaviour, and decision-making confidence. Despite moderate financial literacy among youth, formal financial education remains low, and most participants rely on informal sources such as family and online research for investment advice. **Bindu S. and Cathelina S. (2025)** explored the influence of financial literacy on the financial attitudes of employed women in Bengaluru, Karnataka. Results of the study indicated that financial literacy significantly impacts women's financial independence, saving, and investment behaviour, while education plays a key role in shaping financial knowledge and well-being. However, age and work experience showed limited influence on financial awareness. The study revealed that despite growing awareness of financial concepts, women's participation in financial decision-making remains low due to traditional mindsets and lack of confidence. **Joghee M.V., et al (2025)** conducted a comprehensive study on the factors influencing working women's investment awareness and behaviour. The research examined how financial literacy, income levels, socio-cultural norms, psychological factors, and access to digital financial platforms shape women's financial decision-making. The study found that financial literacy and risk perception significantly affect women's investment confidence, while traditional gender roles and family influence restrict independent decision-making. The study also emphasized the growing importance of digital financial inclusion and workplace financial education in enhancing women's participation in investment activities.

Objectives

As far as the researcher made the literature survey, a vast gap was found that there were no study was found analysing the financial literacy level and its influence on investment decisions particularly with regards to women employees working in healthcare products manufacturing companies. In order to fulfil the gap the researcher has undertaken the study framing the following objectives.

1. To study the socio-economic background and investment attitudes of the respondents.
2. To analyse the financial literacy level of the respondents.
3. To enquire the influence of financial literacy level of the respondents on investment decisions.

METHODOLOGY

Making investments is not an easy task, since good financial knowledge is needed to take right investment decisions. A considerable portion of employees working in various companies manufacturing healthcare products in Thiruvananthapuram are female. Women

make investments in various avenues, but their financial literacy level and decision-making style varies from male employees. The researcher studied the financial literacy level of women employees working in 10 healthcare product manufacturing companies in the study area and how their financial literacy level influenced their decisions towards investments. For this purpose the researcher prepared a well-structured questionnaire and served 50 women employees each from the selected companies. But the researcher could get responses only from 412 respondents. Hence, final sample of the study is confined to 412 respondents. The collected responses were analysed by the researchers using the statistical tools of simple percentage, mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, 't' test, One-way ANOVA and Regression analysis.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are framed for the study,

- There are no significant associations between financial literacy level and socio-economic and investment related variables.
- Financial literacy level of the respondents do not significant influence the investment decisions of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study and discusses the major findings based on the data collected from female employees working in healthcare product manufacturing factories in Thiruvananthapuram. The analysis aims to identify the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, their investment attitudes, levels of financial literacy and its impact on investment decisions of the respondents. The discussion highlights how socio-economic variables, financial awareness, and behavioural aspects shape women's investment decision-making patterns.

Table1: Socio-economic Background of the Respondents

SN	Category	Freq.	%
Marial Status			
1	Married	295	71.6
2	Unmarried	117	28.4
Age			
1	Upto 30 years	72	17.5
2	31 to 40 years	166	40.3
3	41 to 50 years	102	24.8
4	51 to 60 years	72	17.4
Education			
1	Upto school level	86	20.9
2	Under Graduation level	158	38.3
3	Post Graduation level	126	30.6
4	Professional Education	25	6.1
5	Others	17	4.1
Monthly Income			
1	Upto ₹40,000	173	42.0
2	₹40,001 to ₹80,000	107	26.0
3	₹80,001 to ₹1,20,000	79	19.2
4	Above ₹1,20,000	53	12.8
Family Size			
1	Small (Upto 4 members)	148	35.9

2	Medium (5 to 7 members)	186	45.2
3	Large (Above 7 members)	78	18.9
	Total	412	100.0

It is known from table 1 that a majority of the respondents (71.6%) are married, while 28.4% are unmarried. This indicates that most of the female workers have family responsibilities, which could influence their financial priorities, savings habits, and investment preferences. With regard to age, 40.3% of the respondents fall within the 31 to 40 years age group, followed by 24.8% in the 41 to 50 years category. The younger group up to 30 years and those between 51 to 60 years constitute 17.5% and 17.4%, respectively. This shows that the majority of respondents are in their middle working age, typically a stage when income levels are stable and individuals are more likely to make financial and investment decisions. Education-wise classification shows that 38.3% of the respondents have undergraduate-level education, while 30.6% possess postgraduate qualifications. About 20.9% have studied up to school level, 6.1% hold professional qualifications, and 4.1% fall under other categories. This shows that a significant portion of the respondents are well-educated, which is likely to positively influence their financial awareness and investment literacy. However, the presence of around one-fifth with only school-level education indicates that some workers may have limited exposure to financial concepts.

Regarding income levels, 42.0% of the respondents earn up to ₹40,000 per month, followed by 26.0% in the ₹40,001–₹80,000 range. About 19.2% earn between ₹80,001–₹1,20,000, and 12.8% earn above ₹1,20,000. The data indicate that a majority of female workers belong to the lower and middle-income categories. It reveals a need for financial literacy initiatives that help them manage limited resources effectively and make informed investment decisions within their financial capacity. Family size analysis shows that 45.2% of respondents belong to medium-sized families (5–7 members), 35.9% belong to small families (up to 4 members), and 18.9% have large families (above 7 members). This implies that most respondents have moderate family responsibilities, which could impact their saving and investment potential depending on household expenditure patterns.

It is inferred that the socio-economic analysis reveals that the majority of respondents are married, middle-aged, moderately educated, and belong to middle-income families. These characteristics suggest that while they may possess a basic understanding of financial matters, their investment decisions are likely influenced by family responsibilities, income constraints, and moderate risk tolerance. Enhancing financial literacy among this group could significantly improve their capacity for systematic saving, risk management, and rational investment behaviour.

Table 2 brings out the results of investment attitudes of the sample women employees in the study area.

Table 2: Investment Attitude of the Respondents

SN	Category	Freq.	%
Frequency of Investment			
1	Monthly	241	58.5
2	Quarterly	69	16.7
3	Half-yearly	43	10.4
4	Yearly	59	14.3
5	Occasionally		
Average Yearly Investment			
1	Upto ₹50,000	92	22.3

2	₹50,001 to ₹1,00,000	186	45.1
3	₹1,00,000 to ₹1,50,000	71	17.2
4	Above ₹1,50,000	63	15.3
Experience in Making Investments			
1	Upto 5 years	39	9.5
2	5 to 10years	96	23.3
3	10 to 15 years	138	33.5
4	Above 15 years	139	33.7
Primary Source of Awareness			
1	Friends / Relatives	107	26.0
2	Television Media	68	16.5
3	Print Media	45	10.9
4	Social Media	169	41.0
5	Other Sources	23	5.6
Highly Preferred Type of Investment			
1	Equities	43	10.4
2	Mutual Funds	95	23.1
3	Gold & Silver	101	24.5
4	Bonds	36	8.7
5	Bank Deposits	102	24.8
6	Others	35	8.5
	Total	412	100.0

Table 2 reveals that a majority of respondents (58.5%) make investments on a monthly basis, showing a consistent saving and investment habit. Around 16.7% invest quarterly, 10.4% invest half-yearly, and 14.3% invest yearly. The dominance of monthly investors indicates that most women prefer regular and systematic investments, possibly through recurring deposits, mutual fund SIPs, or similar schemes, reflecting financial discipline and awareness of structured saving. Nearly half of the respondents (45.1%) invest between ₹50,001 and ₹1,00,000 per year, while 22.3% invest up to ₹50,000. About 17.2% invest between ₹1,00,001 and ₹1,50,000, and 15.3% invest above ₹1,50,000 annually. This investment pattern shows that most respondents are moderate investors, balancing their income and family needs with their investment potential. Only a smaller proportion of high investors may belong to higher income groups or possess better financial literacy. The majority of respondents have 10 to 15 years (33.5%) or above 15 years (33.7%) of investment experience, showing that two-thirds of the respondents have long-term exposure to financial activities. About 23.3% have 5 to 10 years of experience, while only 9.5% are relatively new to investing (less than 5 years). This indicates that most women have developed financial habits and experience over time, which may positively influence their confidence and ability to make informed financial decisions.

A significant 41.0% of respondents rely on social media as their main source of investment awareness, highlighting the growing role of digital platforms in financial education and promotion. Friends and relatives account for 26.0%, while 16.5% and 10.9% depend on television and print media, respectively. Only 5.6% reported other sources. This exposes that informal and digital networks play a major role in shaping investment awareness among female workers, underlining the importance of credible online financial education initiatives. The most preferred investment options are bank deposits (24.8%) and gold & silver (24.5%), followed closely by mutual funds (23.1%). Investments in equities (10.4%), bonds (8.7%), and other instruments (8.5%) are relatively less favoured. This preference

pattern reveals that most respondents prioritize safe and traditional investments offering stable returns and low risk, which aligns with the typical conservative investment behaviour observed among women.

It is summarised that female workers in healthcare product manufacturing factories exhibit a disciplined but cautious investment attitude. Most invest regularly (monthly) and moderately (up to ₹1 lakh per year), with considerable experience in managing their finances. Their awareness is largely shaped by social media and personal networks, and they prefer secure investment avenues such as bank deposits and precious metals over high-risk options like equities. The results reflect a blend of growing financial participation and traditional risk-averse tendencies, suggesting that enhancing financial literacy could encourage more diversified and strategic investment choices among this group.

Table 3: Financial Literacy Level of the Respondents

SN	Factor	Mean	SD	CV	Rank
1	Basic Financial Knowledge	3.42	1.42	41.52	II
2	Awareness of Investment Avenues	3.65	1.11	30.41	I
3	Risk and Return Awareness	3.12	0.95	30.45	V
4	Financial Information and Analytical Skills	2.86	0.84	29.37	VII
5	Digital Financial Literacy	3.05	1.21	39.67	VI
6	Financial Product Knowledge	3.37	1.04	30.86	III
7	Economic and Policy Awareness	2.75	0.85	30.91	VIII
8	Financial Behaviour and Attitude	3.26	1.13	34.66	IV

The analysis of Table 3 reveals that the overall financial literacy level of female workers in healthcare product manufacturing factories in Thiruvananthapuram is moderate, with notable variations across different dimensions. The highest mean score was observed for awareness of investment avenues (Mean = 3.65) and this aspect has been ranked first. It indicates that most respondents are well-informed about available investment options such as bank deposits, gold, and mutual funds. This is followed by basic financial knowledge (Mean = 3.42) and it was ranked first and financial product knowledge (Mean = 3.37) it was ranked 3rd. These results show a fair understanding of savings, budgeting, and general financial instruments. Respondents also exhibit a reasonably positive financial attitude and behaviour (Mean = 3.26). It shows a tendency toward saving and cautious investing. However, lower mean scores for risk and return awareness (3.12), digital financial literacy (3.05), financial analytical skills (2.86), and economic and policy awareness (2.75) indicate gaps in deeper financial understanding, digital competence, and awareness of broader economic factors. Overall, while the respondents demonstrate awareness and interest in financial matters, their decision-making appears largely traditional and risk-averse, highlighting the need for targeted financial education and digital literacy programs to strengthen analytical capabilities and investment confidence.

It is observed that the respondents possess moderate overall financial literacy. They show strong awareness of investment avenues and basic financial concepts, but relatively weak understanding of analytical skills, economic policy, and risk-return relationships. The results suggest that while female workers are familiar with basic saving and investment options, they often lack deeper knowledge required for strategic and diversified financial decision-making. Enhancing financial education—particularly in digital literacy, analytical skills, and economic awareness—would significantly empower these women to make informed, confident, and goal-oriented investment choices.

Table 4: Association between Financial Literacy & Socio-Economic Variables

S N	Socio-Economic Variables	Tool	t/F Value	Sig.	Ho Result
1	Marital Status	‘t’ Test	2.046	Not Significant	Accepted
2	Age	ANOV A	6.845	Significant	Rejected
3	Education	ANOV A	7.559	Significant	Rejected
4	Monthly Income	ANOV A	1.876	Not Significant	Accepted
5	Family Size	ANOV A	2.013	Not Significant	Accepted

Table 4 reveals that the social variable age and education have a significant association with financial literacy level, as their calculated F-values (6.845 and 7.559 respectively) are statistically significant, leading to the rejection of the null hypotheses. This implies that financial literacy levels differ across age groups and educational backgrounds. On the other hand, the socio-economic variables marital status, monthly income, and family size do not show any significant relationship with financial literacy, as indicated by their non-significant values. This suggests that being married or unmarried, income variations, or household size do not substantially influence one’s level of financial literacy among the surveyed female workers. Overall, the findings indicate that education and age are key determinants of financial literacy, while income and family factors play a relatively minor role. This highlights the importance of promoting financial education programs across all demographic categories, particularly targeting younger and less-educated segments of the workforce to enhance their financial awareness and decision-making capabilities.

Table 5: Association between Financial Literacy & Investment Attitude

S N	Investment Attitudes	Tool	F Value	Sig.	Ho Result
1	Frequency of Investment	ANOV A	1.764	Not Significant	Accepted
2	Average Annual Investment	ANOV A	5.643	Significant	Rejected
3	Experience in Investments	ANOV A	6.118	Significant	Rejected
4	Source of Awareness	ANOV A	1.834	Not Significant	Accepted
5	Preferred Investment	ANOV A	2.003	Not Significant	Accepted

The analysis of Table 5 shows that there is a significant relationship between financial literacy and two factors—average annual investment and experience in investments, as their F-values (5.643 and 6.118, respectively) are statistically significant. It leads to the rejection of the null hypotheses. This indicates that respondents who invest higher amounts annually and those with more years of investment experience tend to possess higher levels of financial literacy. Greater exposure to financial activities appears to enhance understanding, confidence, and awareness regarding investment decisions. However, other

factors such as frequency of investment, source of awareness, and preferred investment type show no significant association with financial literacy, as indicated by their non-significant F-values. This suggests that how often individuals invest, where they obtain investment information, or the type of instruments they prefer (such as gold, bank deposits, or mutual funds) do not necessarily depend on their level of financial literacy.

It is inferred that investment experience and the scale of annual investment are key influencers of financial literacy, implying that practical engagement with financial activities strengthens understanding and informed decision-making. In contrast, habitual or source-based factors have a limited role, emphasizing the importance of experiential learning and structured financial education programs to enhance investment-related literacy among female industrial workers.

Table 7: Influence of Financial Literacy on Investment Decisions

SN	Factor	Mean	SD	CV	Rank
1	Financial Knowledge	3.71	0.96	25.88	II
2	Financial Attitude	3.68	0.85	23.10	III
3	Financial Behaviour	3.51	1.01	28.77	IV
4	Risk Perception	3.21	1.34	41.74	VI
5	Decision-Making Autonomy	3.82	1.22	31.94	I
6	Investment Decision Quality	3.42	1.01	29.53	V
7	Successfulness in Decision	3.11	0.85	27.33	VII

Table 7 reveals that influence of financial literacy on investment decisions in the dimension of “decision-making autonomy” holds the highest mean score (Mean = 3.82, Rank I). It suggests that financially literate respondents are more confident and independent in making their own investment decisions. This reflects a growing sense of empowerment and self-reliance among women when managing financial matters. The next most influential factors are financial knowledge (Mean = 3.71, Rank II) and financial attitude (Mean = 3.68, Rank III). They show that a sound understanding of financial concepts and a positive outlook toward managing money significantly shape investment decisions. Respondents with better financial knowledge and attitudes tend to explore multiple investment avenues and make more rational choices. Financial behaviour (Mean = 3.51, Rank IV) also plays an important role, indicating that regular saving, planning, and disciplined money management contribute positively to effective investment practices. However, lower mean scores were recorded for investment decision quality (Mean = 3.42, Rank V), risk perception (Mean = 3.21, Rank VI), and successfulness in decision (Mean = 3.11, Rank VII). This suggests that while respondents have moderate knowledge and confidence, their ability to assess financial risks and evaluate the outcomes of their investments remains limited. The relatively high coefficient of variation (41.74) for risk perception further indicates wide differences in individuals’ understanding and tolerance of financial risks.

It is inferred that financial literacy positively influences investment decision-making, particularly by enhancing autonomy, knowledge, and attitude. However, there is still scope for improvement in risk assessment and decision evaluation skills. Strengthening practical financial training and awareness programs can help women develop not only confidence and independence in investing but also the analytical capability to make well-informed and successful financial decisions.

Table 8: ANOVA Results under Regression Analysis

Model		Sum Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	179.763	8	22.470	18.525	0.000
	Residual	682.914	563	1.213		
	Total	862.677	571			
Adjusted R Square					0.371	

a. Dependent Variable: Investment Decision; b. Predictors: (Constant), Financial Literacy under various dimensions

Table 8: Regression Analysis of Financial Literacy and Investment Decision

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.418	0.357		6.782	.000
	Basic Financial Knowledge	0.021	0.047	0.022	1.133	0.258
	Awareness of Investment Avenues	0.025	0.046	0.025	1.254	0.211
	Risk and Return Awareness	0.045	0.039	0.050	3.604	0.000
	Financial Information and Analytical Skills	0.026	0.040	0.029	5.432	0.000
	Digital Financial Literacy	0.009	0.047	0.008	2.625	0.009
	Financial Product Knowledge	0.110	0.045	0.103	2.445	0.015
	Economic and Policy Awareness	0.041	0.042	0.042	1.388	0.196
	Financial Behaviour and Attitude	0.013	0.041	0.014	2.543	0.011

a. Dependent Variable: Investment Decisions

In the regression coefficients table, the results show that some dimensions of financial literacy significantly influence investment decisions, while others do not. The financial literacy in the dimensions of Risk and Return Awareness ($\beta = 0.050$, $p = 0.000$), Financial Information and Analytical Skills ($\beta = 0.029$, $p = 0.000$), Digital Financial Literacy ($\beta = 0.008$, $p = 0.009$), Financial Product Knowledge ($\beta = 0.103$, $p = 0.015$), and Financial Behaviour and Attitude ($\beta = 0.014$, $p = 0.011$) are all statistically significant predictors of investment decisions. This implies that respondents who understand the relationship between risk and return, possess strong analytical and digital financial skills, and have sound financial behaviour and product knowledge are more likely to make effective investment decisions.

On the other hand, financial literacy in the dimensions of Basic Financial Knowledge ($p = 0.258$), Awareness of Investment Avenues ($p = 0.211$), and Economic and Policy Awareness ($p = 0.196$) are not significant, indicating that these dimensions do not directly influence investment decisions in this sample. While respondents may have general financial understanding and awareness of available investment options, these factors alone do not necessarily translate into improved decision-making without the ability to analyze, evaluate risks, or apply knowledge in practical investment contexts.

CONCLUSION

The study on financial literacy and investment decisions among female workers in healthcare product manufacturing factories in Thiruvananthapuram reveals that financial literacy plays a crucial role in shaping women's investment behaviour and financial well-being. The findings indicate that most respondents possess a moderate level of financial literacy, with higher awareness of investment avenues and basic financial concepts, but relatively limited understanding of analytical skills, economic policies, and risk-return relationships. Despite being disciplined savers and regular investors, their investment preferences lean toward low-risk options such as bank deposits and gold, reflecting a cautious and traditional financial outlook. The study also evidenced that financial literacy significantly influences investment decisions among female workers in healthcare product manufacturing factories in Thiruvananthapuram. The respondents exhibit a moderate level of financial literacy, with good awareness of investment avenues but limited understanding of risk, analytical skills, and economic policies. Age and education were found to have a strong association with financial literacy, while experience and annual investment also showed a positive relationship. The regression results confirm that dimensions such as risk-return awareness, financial behaviour, product knowledge, and digital literacy greatly impact investment decision-making. Overall, the findings highlight that women with higher financial literacy are more confident and independent in managing their investments. Therefore, enhancing financial education and digital financial training can empower female workers to make better, more informed, and secure investment choices, contributing to their financial independence and economic well-being.

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